

DOE-Guided Development of a Varied Drug Release Cup-Shaped Bilayer Tablet: Delayed-Release Naproxen Sodium and Immediate-Release Misoprostol

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Abstract

Long-term administration of Naproxen Sodium, a potent non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID), is frequently associated with dose-dependent gastrointestinal ulceration, a significant clinical challenge. To mitigate this adverse effect and enhance patient safety, a novel fixed-dose combination tablet was formulated to provide sequential, site-specific release of Naproxen Sodium, and the gastro-protective drug, Misoprostol. The above combination is not available commercially and can be used to prevent the side effects of Naproxen Sodium. However, Naproxen Sodium in combination with Esomeprazole (proton pump inhibitor) is available emphasizing the need for the protection from deleterious effects of Naproxen Sodium on gastric mucosa. Therefore, a fixed dose combination of Naproxen Sodium and misoprostol is proposed and selected for design, development & evaluation of combination product with varied release profile. This was achieved through a unique cup-shaped bilayer novel design, wherein an enteric-coated Naproxen Sodium core is in the lower part of the bilayer tablet and upper layer is placebo followed by enteric coating and film coating to design unique cup shaped bilayer tablet. Misoprostol was placed on the concave shaped cup and dried. The formulation of the Naproxen Sodium core was systematically optimized using a three-factor, two-level factorial Design of Experiments (DoE), which identified the concentration of the super-disintegrant (Croscarmellose sodium) as the most critical variable influencing dissolution. The final scale up batches demonstrated effective gastro-resistance, releasing less than 10% of Naproxen Sodium in acidic media over two hours. Subsequent dissolution testing in pH 6.8 media for Naproxen Sodium and water for Misoprostol confirmed that the release profiles for both drugs were statistically similar to their respective individual marketed products. The calculated similarity factors (f_2) were 69.37 for the delayed-release Naproxen Sodium component and 88.07 for the immediate-release Misoprostol component. This successful application of Quality by Design principles to a novel bilayer tablet design validates its potential as a platform technology for complex, multi-drug release systems.

Keywords - Naproxen Sodium; Misoprostol; Multi-layered tablets; in-vitro drug release; combination products; NSAID; delayed release; enteric coated tablets, bilayer tablets.

I. INTRODUCTION

Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) represent a foundation stone of modern pharmacotherapy for managing pain and inflammation in chronic conditions such as rheumatoid arthritis and osteoarthritis [1]. Naproxen Sodium, a propionic acid derivative, is a prominent member of this class, valued for its potent analgesic and anti-inflammatory properties. Its therapeutic utility however, is counterbalanced by a significant side-effect due to its non-selective inhibition of cyclooxygenase (COX) enzymes [2]. This inhibition disrupts the synthesis of physiologically crucial prostaglandins, particularly within the gastric mucosa, where they maintain the integrity of the protective mucosal barrier [3,4]. The compromise of these essential protective factors renders the stomach mucosa highly susceptible to its own acidic environment, leading to a spectrum of injury ranging from dyspepsia to life-threatening peptic ulceration and haemorrhage [5,6]. Epidemiological studies have

consistently quantified this risk, revealing that chronic NSAID users face a substantially elevated risk for serious gastrointestinal complications [7].

Several formulations have been developed to mitigate this gastrointestinal burden. While selective COX-2 inhibitors were designed to protect the gastric mucosa, concerns regarding their cardiovascular safety profiles have led to a continued reliance on traditional NSAIDs co-prescribed with a gastro protective drugs. Among these drugs, the synthetic prostaglandin E1 analogue, Misoprostol, offers a direct physiological approach by replenishing the very prostaglandins depleted by NSAID therapy [9]. The clinical efficacy of this strategy was explicitly established in important clinical trials, which demonstrated a dramatic reduction in the incidence of NSAID-induced gastric ulcers in patients receiving co-therapy with Misoprostol [10,11].

Despite this proven clinical benefit, the real-world effectiveness of co-therapy is often undermined by poor patient compliance, a challenge that has prompted the development of fixed-dose combinations (FDCs) that combine the NSAID and the gastro protective drug into a single dosage form [12]. However, the development of such an FDC presents a significant pharmaceutical formulation challenge. A simple immediate-release combination would fail to provide the necessary time-based or sequential drug release of both component, as the Misoprostol must be available to exert its protective effect before the Naproxen Sodium is released in GI tract [13,14]. The critical, unmet need is therefore not just for an FDC, but for a novel drug delivery system capable of varied drug release in a precise intervals and in a sequential release of the two drugs from the same dosage form. The above combination is not available in the market and can be used to prevent the side effects of Naproxen Sodium. However, Naproxen Sodium in combination with Esomeprazole (proton pump inhibitor) is available emphasizing the need for the protection from deleterious effects of Naproxen Sodium on gastric mucosa.

This investigation directly addresses this technological gap through the rational design and fabrication of a novel dosage form. We have engineered a unique cup-shaped bilayer design that achieves the pre-requisite physical separation and sequential drug release from the single dosage form [16]. This design formulated such way that, an enteric-coated, delayed-release Naproxen Sodium core in lower layer of cup-shaped bilayer tablet, followed by 3 layers of coating and filling of Misoprostol followed by drying to achieve immediate-release of Misoprostol. The primary objective of this work was to move beyond conceptual design to a demonstrated commercial manufacturing of the dosage form. We sought to develop a robust process for this unique bilayer cup shaped dosage form to provide definitive *in vitro* evidence that this innovative approach could successfully replicate the distinct dissolution profiles of the individual marketed products for Naproxen Sodium and Misoprostol a critical prerequisite for establishing therapeutic equivalence [17].

AIM OF THE STUDY

The aim of this investigation was to address the clinically significant gap between the therapeutic need for gastro-protection during NSAID therapy and the real-world challenges of patient compliance. The central objective was to design, manufacture and comprehensively characterize a novel, single-unit fixed-dose combination tablet capable of delivering Misoprostol immediately and Naproxen Sodium for delayed release. To achieve this, the study focused on two specific goals: 1) To systematically optimize the formulation of Naproxen Sodium core using a Quality by Design (QbD) framework to establish a robust design space 2. To create a provision for the inclusion of low dose drugs 3) To provide definitive *in vitro* evidence, through comparative dissolution testing against marketed products (EC-Naprosyn® for Naproxen Sodium and Arthrotec® - misoprostol part), that this advanced dosage form successfully achieves the required sequential, multi-phasic release profiles necessary for its intended therapeutic benefit.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials: Naproxen Sodium sodium and Misoprostol, Povidone (K-30), Croscarmellose sodium, Magnesium stearate, Eudragit L30 D 55, Sodium hydroxide, Triethyl citrate, Talc, Methanol, and Ethyl Acetate [8] were gift samples by Dr. Reddy's Laboratories, Hyderabad, India. All other excipients and reagents utilized were of analytical or pharmaceutical grade.

2.2 Preparation of the Cup-Shaped Bilayer Tablet: The novel dosage form was fabricated using a sequential manufacturing process encompassing wet granulation, bilayer compression, multi-stage coating and precise liquid filling of Misoprostol [18].

2.2.1 *Naproxen Sodium Granulation (Lower layer component of bilayer tablet)*: The intra-granular components, Naproxen Sodium, lactose monohydrate and Croscarmellose sodium, were co-sifted through an ASTM #20 sieve. Granulation was performed in a Fluid Bed Processor (Top Spray) using an aqueous binder solution of Povidone K-30. The resulting granules were dried to a target loss on drying (LOD) of NMT 7.0% w/w (at 105°C), milled through a co-mill fitted with an 813 µm screen and passed through an ASTM #20 sieve to ensure size homogeneity. The sized granules were blended with extra-granular Croscarmellose sodium before final lubrication with Magnesium stearate (pre-sifted through an ASTM #60 sieve).

2.2.2 *Placebo Layer Blend (Upper layer component of bilayer tablet)*: placebo blend was prepared by co-sifting silicified microcrystalline cellulose (Prosolv HD90 and SMCC 50) and Croscarmellose sodium through an ASTM #20 sieve. Iron oxide a colouring agent, was passed through an ASTM #80 sieve and geometrically mixed with the blend. The mixture was finally lubricated with Sodium Stearyl fumarate (pre-sifted through an ASTM #60 sieve).

2.2.3 *Bilayer Compression*: The Naproxen Sodium and placebo blends were compressed using a bilayer tablet Cadmach compression machine equipped with 12.0 mm round specially designed tooling having upper punch that provides a cup-shape in the upper layer of tablet and to achieve a tablet hardness of 10-14 Kp.

2.2.4 *Sequential Coating and Misoprostol Filling*: The compressed bilayer core tablets were coated with three-stage coating process in a perforated Gansons coater. An initial seal coat of consisting of hydro-alcoholic Hypromellose solution [IPA(30%) and Water (70%)] was applied (the percent solids was 5%w/w), followed by an aqueous dispersion of Eudragit L30D-55 with Triethyl citrate as a plasticizer (10% of TEC) that acts as a functional enteric coat to achieve a target weight gain of 10% w/w. A final film coat of hydro alcoholic Hypromellose and titanium dioxide dispersion [IPA (30%) and Water (70%)] was applied for elegance and protect any interaction with Misoprostol and enteric coating layer [15]. In last stage of manufacturing step, a solution of Misoprostol and Povidone K-30 was prepared in methanol (66.67%) and ethylacetate (33.33%) ratio. This misoprostol solution (~0.33%) was precisely filled into the tablets cavity using a Gilson 215 liquid Handler (~60µL). The filled tablets were subsequently dried in a tray drier at 40°C for 3 hours to remove residual solvents from the tablets.

2.3 Experimental Design and Statistical Optimization

To quantitatively model the influence of critical material attributes (CMAs) on the *in vitro* dissolution of the Naproxen Sodium core and to identify an optimum formulation a systematic, multivariate approach was employed. A three factors, two-level factorial design with three centre-point replicates was constructed using Design-Expert® software, resulting in a total of 11 experimental runs. The inclusion of centre points was critical for assessing experimental error and detecting potential curvature in the design space [19].

The independent variables selected for investigation were key CMAs known to influence tablet matrix properties and dissolution profile are: the concentration of the super disintegrant (Factor A: Croscarmellose sodium), the binder (Factor B: Povidone K-30), and the lubricant (Factor C: Magnesium stearate). Each factor was studied at a low (-1), Optimum (0) and high (+1) level as detailed in Table 1. The low and high values are approximately 15% of the central composition.

Table-1: Composition details of different levels of disintegrant, binder and lubricant

Factors: Formulation Variables	Levels / Quantity Per Unit (Mg)		
	-1	0	1
A: Croscarmellose sodium	9.32	10.96	12.60
B: Povidone PVP-K30	6.99	8.22	9.45
C: Magnesium stearate	2.33	2.74	3.15

The dependent variable, critical quality attribute (CQA) of the dissolution profile: The cumulative percentage of Naproxen Sodium released at 10, 15 and 30 minutes. The resultant data were fitted to a polynomial model to map the response surface. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was employed to determine the statistical

significance of the model and its terms (main effects and interactions), with a p-value of < 0.05 considered significant. The validated model was then used to generate response surface and contour plots to visualize the design space and identify an optimal formulation composition.

2.4 Characterization and Evaluation of the Dosage Form

2.4.1 Drug-Excipient Compatibility Studies: The physicochemical compatibility of Naproxen Sodium with the selected excipients was evaluated using a FTIR spectrometer. Spectra of the pure API and the final lubricated blend were recorded at baseline and after storage for one month under accelerated stability conditions (40°C / 75% RH) over a range of 4000 to 400 cm⁻¹, to identify any potential interactions indicative of instability.

2.4.2 Evaluation of Granules and Tablets: Pre-compression properties of the lubricated blend were determined according to their respective USP general chapters. Bulk and tapped densities were measured using a tapped density tester (USP <616>), from which Carr's compressibility index and the Hausner ratio were calculated. The compressed core and final coated tablets were characterized for critical quality attributes including weight variation (USP <905>), hardness using a calibrated hardness tester, thickness, and friability using a friabilator (USP <1216>).

2.4.3 Drug Content and In-Vitro Release Studies: Drug content (assay) was determined by UV-visible spectrophotometry (Shimadu UV-1800) according to established Pharmacopeial methods. For the assay, a composite of twenty finely powdered tablets, equivalent to one tablet weight, was dissolved in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer, filtered and appropriately diluted for analysis at 332 nm.

The *in vitro* release of both APIs was assessed using a USP Type II (Paddle) dissolution apparatus (Electrolab TDT-08L) at 37 ± 0.5°C and 50 RPM. The dissolution protocol for Naproxen Sodium involved a two-stage acid/buffer challenge: 2 hours in 750 mL of 0.1 N HCl, followed by 60 minutes in 1000 mL of pH 6.8 phosphate buffer. For Misoprostol, release was evaluated in 500 mL of deaerated water over 30 minutes. Aliquots were withdrawn at predefined intervals and analysed by spectrophotometer. The dissolution profiles of the test product were compared against the respective reference products (EC-Naprosyn® and Misoprostol from Arthrotec ®) using the model independent similarity factor, f₂, calculated as:

$$\text{Similarity factor (f}_2\text{)} = 50 \cdot \log \left\{ \left[1 + \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=1}^n (R_t - T_t)^2 \right]^{-0.5} \times 100 \right\}$$

A f₂ value between 50 and 100 indicates that the two dissolution profiles are similar [20].

2.5 Reproducibility at higher scale:

To validate the developed manufacturing process at a representative higher scale, a confirmation batch was manufactured. The quantitative formulation of the optimized N009C Naproxen core and the Misoprostol solution were kept constant. The process was transferred to pilot-scale equipment, ensuring all unit operations fluid-bed granulation, bilayer compression, multi-stage coating and the Misoprostol liquid-fill operation were governed by the same operational principles. All established Critical Process Parameters (CPPs), including granulation spray rate, compression force, functional enteric-coating weight gain and the precise liquid-fill volume, were maintained to ensure process reliability and to challenge the robustness of the entire sequential manufacturing process at higher scale and evaluated using same parameters as above listed in section 2.4

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Drug-Excipient Compatibility Studies: Assessing the physicochemical compatibility of Naproxen Sodium with the selected excipients was a foundational step in development. FTIR spectroscopy was employed as the primary analytical tool for this evaluation.

Figure 1. IR Spectra of Naproxen Sodium API and Blend, Initial

Figure 2. IR Spectra of Naproxen Sodium API and Blend, 40°C/75% RH-1M

Figure 3. IR Spectra of Placebo and Naproxen Sodium Blend, Initial stage

Figure 4. IR Spectra of Placebo and Naproxen Sodium Blend, 40°C/75% RH-1M

Figure 1 provides the baseline comparison of the pure Naproxen Sodium API against the initial (T=0) lubricated blend. The blend's spectrum is, as expected for a high-drug-load formulation, exhibits the absorption bands of the API. A detailed examination confirms that all principal characteristic peaks of Naproxen Sodium are retained in the blend. Specifically, there are no significant shifts observed in the key functional group frequencies, such as the C=O stretch of the carboxylic acid (observed at approximately 1730 cm⁻¹) and the C-H stretching bands (below 3000 cm⁻¹). The blend's spectrum presents as an additive composite of the API and excipients, lacking any evidence of chemical alteration at baseline.

Figure 2 compares the API Initial Vs and drug blend stored at accelerated stability conditions (one month at 40°C / 75% RH). This stressed blend spectrum demonstrates no formation of new absorption bands or significant shifts in the characteristic Naproxen Sodium wavenumbers when compared to the initial blend spectrum (seen in Figure 1). This lack of spectral alteration provides clear evidence that no substantive chemical interaction or degradation occurred. This confirms the API remains chemically stable within the formulation matrix, even under stressed conditions.

Formulation Identity and Specificity (Figures 3 & 4)

The comparisons in Figures 3 and 4 serve a different, but equally critical for analytical purpose: to establish identity and confirm the specificity of the API's spectral characteristics against the excipient matrix. Figure 3 presents the direct overlay of the initial placebo blend against the initial Naproxen Sodium blend. The placebo spectrum was largely without any specific and devoid of the sharp, characteristic absorption bands associated with the Naproxen Sodium API. In clear contrast, the Naproxen Sodium Blend spectrum exhibits the numerous, well-defined peaks characteristic of the API. This comparison confirms that the distinct spectral characteristics observed in the blend is attributable solely to the API and not the excipient matrix.

Figure 4 repeats this identity test using the samples stored for one month at 40°C / 75% RH. The findings are consistent with the initial data. The stressed placebo spectrum remains "blank" with respect to the API's characteristic peaks and the stressed blend spectrum clearly retains all characteristic Naproxen Sodium peaks. This demonstrates that no degradation of the placebo occurred that might create interfering peaks and it reinforces the stability finding from Figure 2. The method is thus confirmed to be specific for identifying Naproxen Sodium in the blend, both at T=0 and after accelerated stability storage.

3.2 Formulation Optimization

A systematic, Design of Experiment (DOE) approach, rooted in Quality by Design (QbD) principles, was employed to optimize the Naproxen Sodium core formulation. This methodology was essential not only for identifying an optimal composition but also for building a deep systematic understanding of how key formulation variables impact the critical quality attribute (CQA) such as dissolution.

3.2.1 Evaluation of pre-compression properties The manufacturability of a tablet formulation is intrinsically linked to the rheological properties of the powder blend. Initial characterization of the pure Naproxen Sodium API revealed poor flow characteristics, evidenced by a high Hausner's ratio (1.66) and a Carr's index (39.74%). Such poor flowability would inevitably lead to inconsistent die filling and significant weight variation during high-speed tableting, precluding a direct compression approach due to high dose of the drug. The implementation of a fluid bed granulation process was therefore a critical process decision.

Table 2: Physical properties of API and granules of different formulations

Batch Number	Factor 1 (A:Croscarmellose Na)	Factor 2 B:Povidone (K-30)	Factor 3 C:Magensium Stearate	Bulk Density (g/mL)	Tapped Density (g/mL)	Compressibility index (%)	Hausner Ratio
API (Naproxen Sodium)	NA	NA	NA	0.414	0.687	39.74	1.66
N001	12.604	9.453	3.151	0.32	0.41	21.95	1.28
N002	9.316	6.987	2.329	0.33	0.42	21.43	1.27
N003	9.316	6.987	3.151	0.32	0.41	21.95	1.28
N004	12.604	6.987	2.329	0.30	0.38	21.05	1.27
N005	9.316	9.453	2.329	0.31	0.39	22.82	1.30
N006	9.316	9.453	3.151	0.31	0.40	22.50	1.29
N007	10.96	8.22	2.74	0.33	0.42	21.43	1.27
N008	10.96	8.22	2.74	0.32	0.42	23.81	1.31
N009	10.96	8.22	2.74	0.30	0.40	25.00	1.33

N010	12.604	6.987	3.151	0.32	0.41	21.95	1.28
N011	12.604	9.453	2.329	0.32	0.40	20.00	1.25

As detailed in Table 2, this unit operation successfully transformed the poorly flowing API into granules with markedly improved properties. The granulated batches consistently demonstrated fair to good flowability, with Hausner's ratios and Carr's indices falling within the acceptable ranges of 1.25-1.33 and 20 - 25%, respectively.

3.2.2 Evaluation of post-compression properties: The predictable and uniform flow was essential for the subsequent development of a robust bilayer compression process and details of the core tablets captured in below table 3.

Table 3: Physicochemical Properties of Core Tablets manufactured as per DoE

Batch Number	Thickness (mm)	Hardness (Kp)	Friability (% w/w)	Disintegration Time (mins)	Avg. weight (mg)	Assay (% w/w)
N001	6.80-6.85	11.9 -12.5	0.1	2'35"	747.2 -749.6	101
N002	6.85-6.90	10.5-11.2	0.2	3'20"	747.7 -748.6	103
N003	6.83-6.88	10.8-11.5	0.1	4'00"	749.3 -751.2	100
N004	6.87-6.92	10.8-11.4	0.1	2'15"	748.2 -749.1	99
N005	6.82-6.87	10.6-11.0	0.2	3'45"	747.4-749.6	101
N006	6.85-6.88	10.9-11.4	0.1	4'10"	749.6 -751.2	99
N007	6.84-6.88	10.8-11.8	0.1	2'25"	747.5 -749.2	102
N008	6.85-6.88	10.6-11.5	0.1	2'40"	749.9 -751.4	101
N009	6.84-6.86	10.8-11.6	0.1	2'30"	747.3 -749.6	101
N010	6.84-6.88	10.7-11.6	0.1	3'30"	749.0 -750.2	101
N011	6.85-6.89	10.8-11.4	0.1	2'25"	747.5-749.2	102

As depicted in the table-3 all formulation exhibited good tablet physical properties and meeting the specification limit like friability- NMT 1.0% and assay limit of 90- 110%.

3.2.3 In-vitro evaluation

As physical properties and chemical assay meeting the requirement, it was decided move ahead with next evaluation of the dissolution profile, which is critical CQA for the core tablets and details explained with DOE experiment details.

Table 4: % drug release of Naproxen Sodium in Core Tablets

B. No.	% drug release of Naproxen Sodium		
	Response 1 (10mins) Dissolution-10 mins	Response 2 (15mins) Dissolution-15 mins	Response 3 (30mins) Dissolution-30 mins
N001	54	74	92
N002	50	68	86
N003	51	69	88
N004	61	78	97
N005	51	69	86
N006	52	72	90
N007	55	71	94
N008	58	73	94
N009	56	72	93
N010	59	77	95
N011	56	76	93

3.2.3.1 Detailed Analysis of Formulation Variables

The factorial design enabled a comprehensive mapping of the formulation design space. The dissolution data from the 11 experimental runs was analysed using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at three distinct time points

10, 15 and 30 minutes to understand the pattern of drug release. This multi-point analysis provided clear, quantitative insights into the specific role of each excipient and their interactions as the tablet disintegrates and dissolves. The key statistical findings for the selected factorial model at each time point are consolidated in Table 5

Table 5: Consolidated ANOVA Results for Naproxen Sodium Dissolution at 10, 15 and 30 Minutes

Source of Variation	10 minutes	15 minutes	30 minutes
	F-value / p-value	F-value / p-value	F-value / p-value
Model	11.79 / 0.0053	40.23 / 0.0002	8.57 / 0.0118
A: Croscarmellose Na	34.64 / 0.0011	135.15 / <0.0001	27.28 / 0.0020
B: Povidone (K-30)	3.28 / 0.1201	—	0.94 / 0.3708
Interaction A×B	7.38 / 0.0348	15.02 / 0.0082	3.03 / 0.1324
Interaction A×C	1.84 / 0.2232	9.08 / 0.0236	3.03 / 0.1324
Lack of Fit	1.07 / 0.5360	0.51 / 0.7444	14.53 / 0.0654

p-values < 0.05 indicate statistical significance.

As evidenced by the highly significant model p-values, a strong and predictable relationship exists between the formulation variables and dissolution performance. The analysis of individual time points reveals a clear, multi-stage mechanism.

Figure 5. Effect of Factor A, B and C on drug releases

Figure 6. Factor AC interactions & design space Figure 7. Factor AB interactions & design space

- **Initial Dissolution Phase (10 mins):** At this early stage, the process is dominated by the powerful effect of the super-disintegrant, Croscarmellose sodium (Factor A), which is the most significant term in the model (p=0.0011). This statistical result has a clear physical correlate: the rapid ingress of water and subsequent

swelling of the disintegrant is the primary event driving the mechanical failure of the tablet matrix. A significant interaction between the disintegrant and the binder (A×B) was also observed ($p=0.0348$). This finding provides a subtle understanding, suggesting that the cohesive, robust granular network formed by the Povidone binder provides a slight resistance to the initial explosive force of the disintegrant, thereby modulating the initial rate of breakup.

- **Intermediate Dissolution Phase (15mins):** The model's predictive power is strongest at the 15-minute mark ($p=0.0002$), a period corresponding to the most rapid rate of drug release. Croscarmellose sodium (Factor A) remains the most critical variable with high significance ($p<0.0001$). While the A×B interaction remains important ($p=0.0082$), a new significant interaction emerges between the disintegrant and the lubricant (A×C) ($p=0.0236$). This is a critical insight. Once the tablet has fractured and the granules are exposed to the medium, the hydrophobic film of Magnesium stearate on the granule surfaces can act as a barrier, impeding further water penetration. This directly counteracts the hydrophilic, wicking action of the disintegrant and this study successfully quantified its significant impact on the dissolution rate.
- **End Dissolution Phase (30 mins):** As the dissolution process nears its endpoint, the model remains significant ($p=0.0118$), but the dynamics have shifted. At this stage, only the main effect of Croscarmellose sodium (Factor A) remains statistically significant ($p=0.0020$). The previously important interactions are no longer influential. This implies that once the granular structure has been largely overcome, the final dissolution of the remaining drug is primarily dependent on the underlying presence of the disintegrant to ensure complete release with the initial influencer effects of the binder and lubricant having already played their part.

This comprehensive analysis allowed for the selection of formulation N009 as the optimized composition. The numerical optimization based on the model predicted a formulation with 11.50 mg Croscarmellose Na, 7.65 mg Povidone (K-30) and 2.37 mg Magnesium Stearate to achieve maximum desirability. Formulation N009 was chosen as it was a robust experimental batch with properties that aligned well with this predicted optimum and design space.

3.3 Optimization of the Functional Enteric Coat: The enteric coating represents a critical process parameter directly linked to the products primary Quality target product profile (QTPP) of preventing gastric release of Naproxen Sodium in acidic media for 2hour. The investigation into the coating level (Table 6) was designed to define a Proven Acceptable Range (PAR) that balanced two competing performance attributes: ensuring robust acid resistance during gastric transit and allowing for rapid, unhindered drug release upon entry into the higher pH environment of the small intestine. The results clearly demonstrated that a coating level of less than 6% w/w was insufficient resulting in a failure to meet the acid-resistance criterion with more than 10% drug release in acidic medium. Conversely, while a 12% w/w coating provided higher acid resistance, it introduced a slight but measurable delay in the subsequent buffer-stage dissolution, suggesting that a thick polymer layer could hinder the rapid de-aggregation of the core. The more than 8% and less than 12% w/w with 10% target coating level was identified range based on the data. The target of 10% coating level provided protection against premature drug release in acidic media meeting the acceptance criteria of NMT10%, while ensuring that the cores intrinsic dissolution characteristics in the pH 6.8 buffer with over 90% of the drug released within 30 minutes similar to market drug product.

Table 6 & Graph-1 Effect of Enteric Coating Level on Naproxen Sodium Release (% Cumulative)

0.1 N HCl (750mL), 2 hrs followed by pH 6.8 Phosphate buffer, 1000 mL, Paddle, 50 RPM			
Time (min)	N009B (8%)	N009C (10%)	N009D (12%)
In 0.1 N hydrochloric acid			
2 hr	5	1	0
In phosphate buffer pH 6.8			
0	0	0	0
5	6	1	0
10	8	4	1
15	58	40	25
20	92	75	55
30	101	93	79
45	102	101	84
60	102	102	90

3.4 Scale-Up Batch Characterization and Process Robustness

To validate the developed process, scale-up batches were manufactured adhering to the established control strategy for the N009C formulation. The execution of the manufacturing process confirmed that all established Critical Process Parameters (CPPs) including granulation, bilayer compression forces, and functional enteric coating weight gain were scaled up to higher scale with using similar parameters to reproduce the results at larger scale.

The resulting tablets from the scale-up batches were comprehensively characterized against all final product specifications. In-process controls (IPCs) and final physical attributes, such as tablet hardness, thickness, and friability, were all found to be well-controlled and compliant with all pre-defined specifications. Furthermore, chemical tests for Assay and Content Uniformity were also found to be within the acceptance criteria of 90-110% w/w. This confirmed the process's ability to produce a consistent, high-quality product at higher scale. The most critical CQA, *in-vitro* dissolution performance, was subjected to a detailed comparative analysis against the marketed products, which is presented in the following section. The final dosage form design presented below:

Figure: 8. Novel cup shaped bilayer tablet design

3.5 Comparative Dissolution Profile (In-Vitro Performance)

The primary objective of the *in-vitro* study was to demonstrate statistical similarity between the developed formulation and the respective marketed reference products. This was first established with the optimized development batch (N009C) and subsequently confirmed with the final scale-up batches, as detailed in Tables 7 and 8. For the delayed-release component (Table 7), the optimized N009C batch demonstrated effective gastro-resistance and a release profile in pH 6.8 buffer that was statistically similar to the reference product EC-Naprosyn®. This was quantitatively confirmed with a calculated f2 similarity factor of 76.89. The subsequent scale-up batches, manufactured as per the control strategy established during the development batches, also demonstrated a similar dissolution profile against the marketed product, achieving an f2 factor of 69.37.

For the immediate-release component (Table 8), the N009C development batch demonstrated the desired rapid dissolution, releasing over 75 % of the Misoprostol within 10 minutes, and yielded an f2 value of 81.17 against the Arthrotec® reference. This performance was successfully reproduced at scale, where the validation batches achieved an f2 similarity factor of 88.07. The successful achievement of f2 similarity (all values >50) for both APIs in both the optimized development batch and the subsequent scale-up batches provides definitive evidence that the complex manufacturing process is well-understood, robust, and reproducible.

Table 7& Graph-2 Comparative Dissolution of Naproxen Sodium (Marketed Product Vs Test)

0.1 N HCl (750mL), 2 hrs followed by pH 6.8 Phosphate buffer, 1000 mL, Paddle, 50 RPM			
Time	Marketed Product	N009C	Scale-up (10%)
In 0.1 N hydrochloric acid			
2hours	1	1	0
In phosphate buffer pH 6.8			
5	2	1	0
10	3	4	3
15	39	40	38
20	78	75	73
30	98	93	91
45	101	101	96
60	103	102	98
f2		76.89	69.37

Table 8 & Graph-3 Comparative Dissolution of Misoprostol (Marketed Product Vs Test)

Time (Min)	Cumulative % drug dissolved		
	Marketed Product	N009C	Scale-up (10%)
0	0	0	0
10	76	79	78
20	85	87	88
30	91	92	94
f2		81.17	88.07

3.5 Overall Control Strategy derived from above experimental data

The overall review of the control strategy based on the above experiments infers that, the identified Critical Material Attributes (CMAs) and Critical Process Parameters (CPPs) to the Quality Target Product profile (QTPP) and Critical Quality Attributes (CQA's) was established robust design space or established range ((PAR) within the studied range. The overall control strategy and scientific justification on the available statistical data presented in table9.

Table 9: Control Strategy Derived from above experimental data

Factor / Parameter	Classification	Established Range (PAR)	Primary Effect on Quality	Scientific Justification
Croscarmellose sodium (factor A)	CMA	3–5% w/w	Enhances disintegration, accelerating Naproxen Sodium release at all stages.	The most critical CMA, statistically significant at all time points ($p \leq 0.0020$). Its level is the primary driver of dissolution. The PAR ensures rapid disintegration to meet the CQA while accounting for its known interactions.
PVP K-30 (Binder) (factor B)	CMA	12–16% w/w	Provides granule cohesion and mechanical robustness, ensuring optimal tablet hardness (10-14 Kp).	While not a significant main factor, its interaction with the disintegrant (A×B, $p=0.0348$) was proven to modulate the initial release rate. The PAR is set to balance the need for granule strength against the risk of slowing dissolution.
Magnesium stearate (factor C)	CMA	0.5–1% w/w	Improves blend compressibility and lubrication for manufacturability.	Its antagonistic interaction with the disintegrant (A×C, $p=0.0236$) was found to be significant. This justifies the narrow PAR, which prevents the lubricant's hydrophobicity from negatively impacting the CQA of dissolution.
Enteric coating gain	CPP	8–12% w/w and 10% is optimum	Provides gastric resistance, preventing premature drug release in acid NMT 10% release in 2h and desired release in buffer stage.	This range is critical for functional performance. Data showed <8% failed gastric resistance (~6% release), while >12% impeded buffer release. The PAR ensures the QTPP for delayed release is met.
Protective HPMC film coat	CPP	4–6% w/w	Prevents Misoprostol	Process development confirmed this PAR provides a uniform,

			degradation by avoiding contact with the acidic enteric polymer.	continuous film layer sufficient to protect the chemically labile Misoprostol interaction with enteric coating layer.
Compression force	CPP	Optimized to 10-14 Kp Hardness	Ensures robust interlayer adhesion and precise cavity formation.	This range ensures the tablet matrix integrity required for the disintegrant and binder to function as predicted by the DOE model. Forces outside this range resulted in lamination or poor adhesion.
Granulation spray rate / drying temperature	CPP	Optimized during development	Controls critical granule attributes (moisture, particle size and flow).	These parameters were optimized to consistently produce granules with the target attributes (LOD NMT 7.0%, Hausner Ratio < 1.3) necessary for free flowing of the granules and less weight variation at compression stage.

IV. CONCLUSION

This novel formulation design with varied drug release lead to a viable and innovative pharmaceutical formulation through the systematic application of formulation science and Quality by Design principles. The primary objective to create a fixed-dose combination tablet that could ensure patient compliance for effective analgesic and anti-inflammatory treatment while providing effective gastroprotective therapy was achieved by engineering a novel, cup-shaped bilayer dosage form using design of experiment principles.

The implementation of a Quality by Design (QbD) framework, utilizing a factorial Design of Experiments, provided the essential functional basis for the rational development of Naproxen Sodium core. This approach enabled the deconvolution of complex variable interdependencies, yielding a predictive quantitative model that accurately described the impact of critical material attributes on *in vitro* drug release kinetics. The resulting statistical model identified the super disintegrant concentration (Croscarmellose sodium, $p < 0.0001$) as the principal factor controlling the rate and extent of drug dissolution. Critically, this analysis also quantified the significant, antagonistic interactions between the disintegrant and both the binder ($p = 0.0348$) and lubricant ($p = 0.0236$), thereby interpreting the secondary mechanisms that modify the overall drug release profile.

These functional insights were leveraged to establish a robust control strategy, transitioning the development process from an empirical to a science-based paradigm. The description of a design space, with established Proven Acceptable Ranges for these CMAs, provides a framework to ensure lot-to-lot consistency and mitigate the risk of manufacturing process deviations. The development of a well-characterized, robust core tablet with predictable performance was a critical prerequisite for its successful integration into the final, complex bilayer dosage form.

The final, optimized dosage form performed precisely as intended. It demonstrated meeting the acceptance criteria for gastro-resistance as per Compendial recommendation of NMT 10% (~1%) of Naproxen Sodium release during the 2-hour acid resistance test and providing rapid and complete release in the pH 6.8 media. Crucially, the *in vitro* dissolution profiles of both active ingredients from the optimized N009C batch were shown to be statistically similar to their respective Marketed products, with f_2 similarity factors of 76.89 for Naproxen Sodium and 81.17 for Misoprostol. This successful outcome was confirmed during process validation, where the scale-up batches also demonstrated bio-mimetic dissolution profiles, achieving f_2 values of 69.37 (Naproxen) and 88.07 (Misoprostol) against the reference products. This provides strong evidence that the complex, varied drug release characteristics required for therapeutic equivalence have been successfully formulated and are reproducible at scale.

The current novel research work not only presents a promising therapeutic alternative for patients requiring long-term NSAID therapy but also validates a novel bilayer cup shaped tablet design as an adaptable platform technology for the development of future complex FDC products with chemical incompatibility or varied drug release requirement.

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